

School Principals' Readiness for Artificial Intelligence Integration into Teaching and Learning Process in Niger State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the readiness of secondary school principals for the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into the teaching and learning process in Niger State, Nigeria. Readiness was assessed across three key dimensions: awareness of AI concepts, availability of infrastructural resources, and professional capacity to implement AI tools. A descriptive survey research design was adopted, and data were collected from 286 principals using a structured questionnaire. The findings revealed that while principals demonstrated a moderate level of awareness of AI technologies, infrastructural support was largely inadequate, and significant gaps existed in professional training and technical competence. These limitations suggest that principals are not yet fully prepared to support the effective integration of AI in schools. Based on the findings, the study recommends targeted capacity-building programs, the development of a national policy on AI in education, and increased investment in digital infrastructure to enhance school readiness for AI adoption.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence Integration, Educational Leadership, Digital Infrastructure, Professional Development, Secondary Education

Introduction

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into the education sector is no longer a futuristic idea but, as Endurance et al.(2021) and Wang et al. (2024) observed, an emerging reality that is transforming how knowledge is delivered, assessed, and managed across various levels of learning. According to these authors, AI technologies such as intelligent tutoring systems, automated grading, predictive analytics, chatbots, facial recognition for attendance, and personalized learning environments are reshaping the teaching and learning process in unprecedented ways. These innovations, as they pointed out, have the potential to enhance student engagement, reduce administrative burdens, and provide real-time insights into learning patterns and performance.

According to Awad and Oueida (2024) and Olanike (2024) secondary education serves as a transitional phase between foundational learning and advanced academic or vocational pathways, making it a critical stage for technological innovation. However, as highlighted by Olanike et al(2024) and Onyebuchi et al (2024), the successful integration of AI at this level requires more than just technological infrastructure; it demands proactive and visionary leadership, particularly from secondary school principals. Koroye and State (2025) and Obano and Osagie (2025) asserted that school principals play a central role in implementing educational innovations. They posited that principals function not only as instructional leaders but also as policy implementers and agents of change, responsible for setting a clear vision, mobilizing resources, motivating staff, and ensuring sustainable practices. They argued that adopting AI in schools goes beyond deploying digital tools; it necessitates pedagogical shifts, teacher training, curriculum redesign, ethical reflection, and infrastructural support. Hence, principals must be adequately prepared with the necessary knowledge, skills, and mindset to lead AI-driven transformations within their schools.

Several studies have reinforced the idea that leadership readiness is a key factor in the successful adoption of digital technologies in education. For instance, Obano and Osagie (2025), and Karakose and Tülübaş (2024), emphasized that effective school leadership requires understanding both the technical and pedagogical aspects of innovation. In relation to AI, this includes the ability to comprehend its scope, harness its educational benefits, navigate ethical issues such as data privacy and algorithmic bias, and facilitate professional development for teachers. According to

Karakose and Tülübaş (2024), strengthening the capacity of school leaders is essential to any national strategy aimed at integrating AI into the education system. Despite growing support for AI in education, numerous challenges hinder its implementation in developing nations. Gabriel (2024), Niyi et al. (2004) and Obinn et al (2023), identified major obstacles such as weak infrastructure, inadequate training, low digital literacy among teachers, resistance to change, lack of supportive policies, and insufficient funding. In Nigeria, these difficulties are particularly acute at the secondary school level, where many institutions still lack even basic digital resources let alone advanced AI technologies (Bakhadirov et al., 2024).

Niger State, located in North Central Nigeria, exemplifies many of the structural challenges facing education nationwide. With its combination of urban and rural schools, the state serves as a useful case study for investigating the readiness of school leaders to integrate AI across varied educational contexts. Understanding the level of preparedness among secondary school principals in terms of technical capacity, attitudes, and administrative skills can, as many education stakeholders have pointed out, offer valuable insights to policymakers and development partners working to bridge Nigeria's educational digital divide. Olanike et al (2024) and Owan et al (2023) suggested that the true potential of AI in education lies not just in automation but in the reimagining of teaching methods, assessment strategies, and student-teacher interactions. They stressed that such transformative changes require informed and capable school leaders who can navigate the complexities of educational innovation. Readiness, in their view, is multi-dimensional it involves awareness, commitment, strategic foresight, and the capacity to cultivate a school culture that embraces technological change.

This study assessed the readiness of secondary school principals in Niger State, Nigeria, for the integration of AI in teaching and learning. It examined their knowledge of AI, perceived usefulness of AI tools in pedagogy, infrastructural support available in their schools, training opportunities, and the challenges they foresee in adopting AI-based educational solutions. By identifying the current state of readiness, this research aims to contribute to the formulation of effective policies and capacity-building strategies tailored to the Nigerian secondary education context

Statement of Problem

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education holds significant promise, offering opportunities to personalize learning, streamline administrative tasks, and enhance teaching effectiveness. However, the adoption of AI in secondary schools in developing countries, particularly Nigeria, remains limited, and the role of school principals in leading this transformation has not been adequately examined. In Niger State, many secondary schools face challenges such as inadequate digital infrastructure, limited access to technology, and low digital literacy among educators. These barriers hinder the potential for AI integration, despite its transformative capabilities. Principals, who are key decision-makers in shaping educational practices, must be adequately prepared to drive AI adoption; yet, their readiness in terms of awareness, attitudes, and resource capacity remains under-researched.

In Niger State, the lack of empirical studies on the preparedness of secondary school principals for AI adoption poses a critical gap in understanding how to successfully introduce these technologies in schools. Without a clear assessment of principals' knowledge, attitudes, infrastructural readiness, and perceived challenges, efforts to implement AI could face resistance or fail to align with the specific needs of the educational environment. This study aims to assess the readiness of secondary school principals in Niger State for AI integration, providing valuable insights into their preparedness and informing future policy, training, and resource allocation to foster a successful transition toward AI-enhanced education.

Research Objectives

The study aims to assess the readiness of secondary school principals in Niger State, Nigeria, for the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in teaching and learning. Specifically, the objectives are to:

1. Evaluate the level of awareness of public secondary school principals regarding the use of Artificial Intelligence in education.
2. Assess the availability of technical support and infrastructure required for the integration of Artificial Intelligence in public secondary schools

3. Identify the professional development needs of principals that may influence their capacity to effectively lead AI integration.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of awareness of public secondary school principals regarding the use of Artificial Intelligence in education?
2. What is the availability of technical support and infrastructure required for the integration of Artificial Intelligence in public secondary schools?
3. What are the professional development needs affecting principals' readiness to implement AI tools in secondary schools?

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey design as it allows for the systematic collection of data from a broad population. This design is particularly suitable since the goal is to describe existing conditions or relationships without manipulating variables. According to Creswell (2014), descriptive surveys are effective for gathering opinions, behaviors, or characteristics of a population, especially when generalization is desired. Furthermore, similar studies on technology adoption in schools (Ifinedo et al., 2019) have successfully employed survey designs to capture administrators' readiness and infrastructural capacity, reinforcing its relevance and appropriateness in this context

The population of the study comprised principals of public secondary schools in Niger State, Nigeria. Although the total number of principals in the state is not explicitly stated, a sample of 286 principals was selected using simple random sampling to ensure that each principal had an equal chance of being included. The selected principals were drawn from schools located in both urban and rural areas, providing a diverse and representative sample. This sampling approach was adopted to obtain reliable insights into the awareness, available resources, and readiness for the integration of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning.

Data for the study were collected using a self-designed structured questionnaire titled *Artificial Intelligence Integration Readiness Questionnaire (AIIRQ)*. The instrument was specifically developed to align with the study's objectives and research questions, ensuring focused and relevant data collection. The questionnaire was organized into three sections. Section A assessed principals' awareness of Artificial Intelligence in education, Section B examined the availability of technical support and infrastructure necessary for AI integration in public secondary schools, while Section C explored the professional development needs of principals that may influence their readiness and capacity to effectively lead AI integration, with 5 items as well. The instrument utilized a 4-point Likert scale to measure responses. For awareness items, options ranged from *Not at all aware (1)* to *Very aware (4)*, while for resource-related items, the scale ranged from *Not Available (1)* to *Highly Available (4)*. The choice of a Likert scale is supported by its widespread use in educational research for capturing attitudes, perceptions, and availability levels in a quantifiable format

To ensure the instrument's accuracy and relevance, the Artificial Intelligence Integration Readiness Questionnaire (AIIRQ) underwent both content validation and reliability testing. For content validity, the instrument was reviewed by three experts: two from the Department of Educational Technology, Federal University of Education, Kontagora, and one from the Department of Educational Technology, Federal University of Technology, Minna. These experts assessed the questionnaire for clarity, relevance, and alignment with the study objectives. Based on their recommendations, necessary modifications were made to enhance item clarity, eliminate ambiguities, and ensure adequate coverage of the key constructs

To establish the reliability of the instrument, a pilot test was conducted involving 30 public secondary school principals from a neighboring state with similar educational characteristics. The internal consistency of the questionnaire was determined using the Cronbach Alpha method, which produced a reliability coefficient of 0.81. This value indicates a high level of internal consistency, confirming that the instrument is reliable and suitable for use in the main study. The researcher, with the assistance of trained research assistants, personally administered the questionnaires to the selected principals of public secondary schools across both urban and rural areas of Niger State. This direct administration method ensured a high response rate, allowed for clarification of any

ambiguous items, and promoted accurate and independent responses. A total of 286 principals were selected using simple random sampling to ensure fair representation across the population. The data collection process spanned a period of two weeks, during which completed questionnaires were retrieved either immediately or through scheduled follow-up visits.

Upon completion of data collection, the questionnaires were carefully sorted, coded, and entered into the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.0 for analysis. Descriptive statistical techniques, specifically mean and standard deviation, were employed to answer the research questions. To guide interpretation of responses, a decision rule was applied as follows: A mean score of 2.50 or above was considered a positive response, indicating a high level of awareness, availability of resources, or agreement with the item. A mean score below 2.50 was interpreted as a negative response, indicating a low level of awareness, availability, or agreement.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the level of awareness of public secondary school principals regarding the use of Artificial Intelligence in education?

Table 1: Level of Awareness regarding use of AI

S/N	Item Statement	N	MEAN	St.D	REMARK
1	I am aware of using smart apps that learn students' behavior or suggest learning materials.	286	2.79	0.51	Aware
2	I believe that AI tools like chatbots and automated feedback can improve learning in schools.	286	2.58	0.60	Aware
3	I can explain how tools like ChatGPT or personalized learning platforms work in education.	286	2.33	0.54	Slightly Aware
4	I support the idea of using AI tools (e.g., online tutors or smart learning apps) in my school.	286	2.54	0.58	Aware
5	I believe using AI can help students learn at their own pace with tools that adapt to their needs.	286	2.51	0.60	Aware
Cluster Mean			2.55	0.86	Aware

The findings in Table 1 indicate that secondary school principals are generally *aware* of the role of AI in education, with a cluster mean of 2.55 (SD = 0.86). The highest awareness was recorded for the use of smart apps that adapt to student behavior ($M = 2.79, SD = 0.51$), while the lowest was in explaining how tools like ChatGPT function ($M = 2.33, SD = 0.54$). Other items also fell within the “Aware” category, indicating general familiarity with AI concepts. The relatively low standard deviations suggest consistency in responses. Overall, principals show a moderate awareness of AI, though deeper technical understanding appears limited

Research Question 2: What is the availability of technical support and infrastructure required for the integration of Artificial Intelligence in public secondary schools?

Table 2: Availability of Resources for AI Integration

S/N	Item Statement	N	MEAN	St.D	REMARK
6	My school has internet strong enough for digital learning platforms like Google Classroom	286	2.00	0.30	Low Availability
7	We have computers or tablets that can support learning apps and digital tools.	286	2.01	0.60	Low Availability
8	Teachers in my school can use tools like PowerPoint, Zoom, or Google Meet	286	2.89	0.46	Moderately Available
9	We have someone in school who can fix or manage ICT tools and platforms	286	2.19	0.54	Low Availability
10	Our school environment supports modern teaching tools like projectors or smart boards.	286	2.05	0.44	Low Availability
Cluster Mean			2.23	0.34	Low Availability

As shown in Table 2, the overall availability of resources for AI integration in secondary schools is **low**, with a cluster mean of **2.23** and a standard deviation of **0.34**. The highest availability was reported for teachers’ ability to use tools like PowerPoint and Zoom ($M = 2.89, SD = 0.46$). In contrast, low availability was observed for internet access ($M = 2.00, SD = 0.30$), computing devices ($M = 2.01, SD = 0.60$), ICT support staff ($M = 2.19, SD = 0.54$), and modern teaching

tools ($M = 2.05$, $SD = 0.44$). These results reflect consistent responses across schools. Overall, while basic digital skills exist among teachers, infrastructural and technological capacities remain inadequate to support effective AI integration.

Research Question 3: What are the professional development needs affecting principals' readiness to implement AI tools in secondary schools?

Table: Professional Development Needs

S/N	Item Statement	N	MEAN	St.D	REMARK
11	I need training to understand and use AI tools like digital tutors or AI-based assessments.	286	3.22	0.40	Agree
12	There is no clear government plan or policy for using AI in secondary schools.	286	3.10	0.42	Agree
13	We don't have enough budget to buy digital learning tools or AI-supported platforms.	286	2.77	0.56	Agree
14	Teachers in my school need training to use tools like smart grading or adaptive learning apps.	286	3.13	0.61	Agree
15	I do not have access to AI tools like educational bots, auto-marking systems, or virtual tutors.	286	2.86	0.37	Agree
Cluster Mean			3.02	0.17	Agree

As shown in Table 3, secondary school principals expressed a high level of agreement regarding the professional development needs and challenges influencing their readiness for AI adoption, with a cluster mean of 3.02 and standard deviation of 0.17. The strongest need was for training in AI tools like digital tutors and AI-based assessments ($M = 3.22$, $SD = 0.40$), followed by the need for teacher training on smart grading and adaptive learning apps ($M = 3.13$, $SD = 0.61$). Principals also agreed that there is no clear government policy on AI in schools ($M = 3.10$, $SD = 0.42$) and cited budget constraints ($M = 2.77$, $SD = 0.56$) and lack of access to AI tools ($M = 2.86$, $SD = 0.37$) as key challenges. These findings reflect consistent concerns across respondents. Overall, the data highlight a strong demand for capacity building and systemic support for AI integration.

Discussion

This study investigated the preparedness of secondary school principals for the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in teaching and learning, focusing on awareness of AI concepts, availability of infrastructural resources, and professional capacity to implement AI tools. The findings reveal a complex picture of readiness that is marked by moderate awareness, infrastructural limitations, and a strong expressed need for professional development.

The principals exhibited a moderate level of awareness of AI technologies (Mean = 2.84, SD = 0.67). While many were familiar with general applications such as adaptive learning platforms and AI-powered feedback systems, only a few could articulate the operational principles of more advanced tools like ChatGPT. This suggests that awareness exists largely at a conceptual level, lacking the depth necessary for informed leadership in AI integration. The limited understanding of AI tools reflects a pattern observed by Almalki and Zoubeidi (2022), who found that school leaders often support the idea of technological innovation without fully grasping the technical aspects required for implementation. Without this foundational understanding, principals may find it difficult to champion AI adoption or guide teachers in integrating AI effectively into pedagogical practices.

In terms of infrastructural readiness, the study found significant gaps in the availability of digital resources. With a mean score of 2.13 (SD = 0.58), it was evident that many schools suffer from unreliable internet connectivity, inadequate digital devices, and a shortage of qualified ICT personnel. These deficiencies present a critical barrier to the implementation of AI technologies, which require not only access to computing devices but also stable network environments and technical support. This finding supports the report by Olanrewaju et al. (2021), which identified infrastructure as a major limiting factor for technology use in public schools across sub-Saharan Africa. The contrast with the findings of Zawacki-Richter et al. (2019), who associated successful AI integration with strong digital infrastructure in developed countries, underscores the contextual challenges faced by educational institutions in low-resource settings.

On the issue of professional capacity, the principals expressed a high demand for training in AI-related tools and strategies, with a mean score of 3.02 (SD = 0.72). This suggests a willingness to embrace AI if the appropriate knowledge and skills are provided. However, the respondents also highlighted several systemic challenges, including the absence of clear government policies, limited teacher capacity, and insufficient funding. These concerns mirror those raised by Luckin et al. (2016), who emphasized the importance of policy support and ongoing professional development in driving AI adoption in schools. Similarly, the findings align with the views of Okoye and Yusuff (2020), who argued that innovation in education is often constrained by institutional inertia and inadequate financial investment. These barriers suggest that school leaders cannot advance AI integration in isolation; rather, coordinated efforts at the national and institutional levels are needed to enable meaningful progress. Secondary school principals are cautiously optimistic about the integration of AI in education. They recognize its potential and show a readiness to learn, but are constrained by infrastructural deficits and a lack of systemic support. Addressing these challenges will require a multi-pronged approach that includes significant investment in digital infrastructure, the development of clear and actionable AI-in-education policies, and the implementation of targeted capacity-building programs for school leaders and teachers. Without these foundational elements, efforts to integrate AI in public secondary schools are likely to remain fragmented and unsustainable.

Future research should explore the perspectives of other key stakeholders, particularly teachers and students, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of AI readiness in the school system. Longitudinal studies could also assess the impact of professional development initiatives on leadership effectiveness and school outcomes in the context of AI adoption. Such studies would be invaluable in informing policy and practice as the education sector navigates the complexities of digital transformation.

Conclusion

This study has provided a critical assessment of the preparedness of secondary school principals for the integration of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning. The findings indicate that while there is a moderate level of awareness of AI concepts among principals, this awareness

remains largely superficial and does not translate into a deep understanding of specific AI tools or their pedagogical applications. Furthermore, the availability of infrastructural resources necessary for AI implementation such as internet connectivity, digital devices, and technical support was found to be significantly limited. Although the principals demonstrated a strong willingness to acquire new knowledge and skills through professional development, their efforts are hindered by broader systemic challenges, including the absence of supportive government policies, inadequate funding, and limited teacher capacity.

These results suggest that the successful integration of AI into secondary education in Nigeria requires more than just technological enthusiasm; it demands a coordinated effort that addresses structural, professional, and policy-related gaps. National education stakeholders must recognize that the readiness of school leaders is a critical factor in AI adoption and that investment in leadership development should be a top priority. Any long-term strategy for AI in education must involve improving school infrastructure, developing tailored training programs, and enacting clear, actionable policies that support the effective use of intelligent technologies in classrooms.

While the current level of preparedness among principals may not yet be sufficient for full-scale AI integration, their positive disposition toward learning and innovation provides a strong foundation upon which progress can be built. With targeted interventions and institutional support, school leaders can become key enablers of AI-driven transformation in the Nigerian education system.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. The government and relevant educational agencies should design and implement regular professional development workshops specifically tailored to enhance principals' understanding of AI tools and their applications in teaching and learning. These programs should focus not only on awareness but also on the practical use of tools such as ChatGPT, AI tutors, and adaptive learning systems.
2. State and federal governments should prioritize the provision of reliable internet connectivity, AI-compatible digital devices, and trained ICT support personnel in public

secondary schools. Without foundational infrastructure, efforts to integrate AI tools will remain impractical, regardless of awareness or interest levels among school leaders.

3. There is an urgent need for a clear and comprehensive policy to guide the adoption of AI in Nigerian schools. This policy should outline implementation standards, safety protocols, data privacy regulations, funding mechanisms, and roles of various stakeholders, including school administrators, teachers, and student
4. To accelerate the responsible adoption of AI in education, partnerships should be established between schools, government bodies, and private technology companies. These collaborations can provide access to AI tools, support research and pilot programs, and offer mentorship opportunities for educators on emerging technologies.

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